

PHRASEOLOGICAL EQUIVALENCE IN TRANSLATION

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Abstract

This article examines translation using phraseological equivalence as one of the most effective strategies for rendering phraseological units from the source language into the target language. The study analyzes the main criteria of this method, its advantages, and its limitations, as well as the influencing of cultural and linguistic factors influencing and interpretation of phraseological units. The research aims to enhance understanding of how phraseological equivalence may contribute to semantic accuracy, stylistic adequacy, and pragmatic effect in translation.

Keywords: phraseological units, phraseological equivalence, idioms, semantic equivalence, imagery correspondence, pragmatic adequacy, cross-cultural communication.

1. Introduction

Phraseology is a branch of linguistics that studies fixed expressions such as idioms and set phrases which meanings cannot be derived from the senses of their individual components. Phraseological units are characterized by lexical stability, grammatical fixedness, and figurative meaning. According to Masimova, phraseological units represent stable word combinations in which the meaning is transferred from the individual components to the whole expression.[2;11]

Many phraseological units are deeply rooted in national culture, traditions, and historical experience. Baker [1;92] states that idioms containing culture-specific elements are not necessarily untranslatable; rather, the main difficulty lies in conveying their meaning and cultural associations. Phraseological units play a significant role in cross-cultural communication, as they reflect the worldview, values, and mentality of a speech community.

One of the most effective methods of translating phraseological units is translation using a phraseological equivalence. This method involves rendering a phraseological unit from the source language by a phraseological unit in the target

language that fully matches in meaning, imagery, stylistic coloring, and pragmatic effect. Despite its effectiveness, the selection of full equivalence often remains subjective and depends largely on the translator's experience and intuition. Therefore, a systematic analysis of this method is required.

2. Methodology

The present study applies four main criteria to determine whether a phraseological unit in the target language can be considered a full equivalent of a source-language unit. These criteria include semantic equivalence, imagery correspondence, stylistic matching, and pragmatic adequacy.

Example 1: *"Kill two birds with one stone"* ↔ *"Bir o'q bilan ikki quyonni urmoq"*.

Both phraseological units share the same meaning, which is accomplishing two tasks with a single action. The imagery is similar, and both idioms are stylistically neutral and commonly used in everyday speech.

Example 2: *"Add fuel to the fire"* ↔ *"Olovga moy sepmoq"*

In this case, both idioms convey the idea of worsening an already negative situation. The metaphorical imagery and stylistic usage correspond closely, fulfilling all four criteria.

3. Results

The analysis of phraseological units in Mark Twain's *The Adventures of Tom Sawyer* and its Uzbek translation shows that only about 15–25% of phraseological units can be translated using phraseological equivalences. These are mainly idioms based on universal metaphors or shared human experiences.

For example:

- *"Rolling in wealth"* → *"boyib ketmoq"*
- *"Heart breaks"* → *"vijdonan azoblanmoq"*

These examples demonstrate semantic and pragmatic correspondence between the source and target expressions. However, many culture-specific idioms such as *"playing hookey"* or *"whitewash a fence"* do not have full equivalents in Uzbek and therefore require alternative translation strategies.

4. Discussion

The limited number of phraseological equivalences can be explained by cultural, historical, and cognitive differences between English and Uzbek. While some idioms are based on universal human emotions and experiences, many others reflect culture-specific realities that cannot be directly transferred into another language.

Despite their limited availability, phraseological equivalences are highly valuable when they exist. They allow translators to preserve semantic meaning, stylistic expressiveness, and emotional coloring simultaneously. However, excessive reliance on this method may lead to forced or unnatural translations if contextual and pragmatic factors are ignored. Therefore, translators must carefully evaluate the suitability of a phraseological equivalence in each specific context.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, translation using phraseological equivalences is one of the most effective strategies for rendering phraseological units in literary translation. This method ensures a high degree of semantic accuracy and stylistic naturalness while maintaining the cultural and emotional impact of the original text. However, due to cultural and linguistic differences between languages, full equivalents are not always available.

When full equivalence cannot be achieved, translators should apply alternative methods such as partial equivalents, analogues, or descriptive translation to ensure communicative adequacy. Overall, the study highlights the importance of a flexible and context-sensitive approach to phraseological translation, contributing to more accurate and culturally appropriate translations.

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